

A background image showing a large pile of dark brown wood chips, with a curved orange border at the bottom.

ESTIMATING POST-CONSUMER FIBREBOARD WASTE GENERATION IN EUROPE

Medium-density fibreboard (MDF) is a wood-based panel widely used in furniture manufacturing, interior design and construction. However, limited information is available on the lifespan of MDF-based products and, therefore, when they are likely to become waste. To support better decision-making of market actors who recycle MDF, the EcoReFibre project has developed an open-access interactive tool that estimates the current fibreboard waste volumes and future volumes to 2050.

European MDF/HDF end-uses in 2023, data: EPF

FROM OFFICIAL STATISTICS TO EUROPEAN APPARENT CONSUMPTION

The model behind the tool is built on apparent consumption, calculated from production, import and export data published by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). This indicator reflects the quantity of fibreboard entering a given market each year. Combined with product lifespan data collected during the project, it helps predict when this material will become waste.

To refine the estimates, FAO data were combined with data from the European Panel Federation (EPF) on the share of fibreboard production allocated to different product categories. These categories have different average lifespans, for example doors typically last longer than toys.

The apparent fibreboard consumption does not include fibreboard embedded in imported products, such as furniture or interior fittings. No reliable method was found to estimate these volumes. The tool therefore allows users to add an additional fibreboard volume to account for this potential source of fibreboard waste.

AN INTERACTIVE AND TRANSPARENT TOOL

Through an intuitive interface, users can adjust key parameters such as product lifespan, additional fibreboard from imports, geographical scope and future consumption trends. Product lifespans are based on a large-scale survey of end-users, reflecting real replacement behaviour. By combining consumption data and lifespan distributions, the model estimates when fibreboard produced in the past is likely to enter the waste stream and become available for recycling. Historical estimates draw on published statistics up to 2023, and the input dataset can be refreshed as new annual statistics become available.

The tool also supports scenario exploration where, “optimistic”, “conservative” and “pessimistic” refer to high, moderate and low fibreboard consumption. Accordingly, users can create scenarios of optimistic consumption, shorter product lifespans and higher imports of fibreboard-containing products that will predict higher waste volumes. At the other extreme, scenarios can assume declining consumption, longer product lifespans and limited imports. Even under pessimistic, and conservative assumptions, the tool forecasts substantial fibreboard waste volumes in the coming decades, emphasising the importance of developing dedicated recycling solutions (cf. screenshot of the tool interface on page 5).

Developed jointly by FCBA and ESB, the tool is freely available on the EcoReFibre website, with a user guide. All results can be downloaded as raw data for further analysis. Beyond current estimates, the tool helps stakeholders to explore future pathways, inform investment and policy discussions, and anticipate the role of fibreboard recycling in a circular economy.

Preview of the EcoReFibre interactive tool available on the website.

↑
Scan to open the tool.

ANALYSIS OF POST-CONSUMER WOOD WASTE IN FRANCE

EcoReFibre carried out a three-year study in France to understand what wood products enter the wood waste stream, with a specific focus on the share of post-consumer fibreboard.

ESB collected and analysed around 1.5 tonnes of post-consumer wood waste using a standardised protocol. In the lab, samples were sieved, and the coarse fraction was manually sorted into solid wood, fibreboard, other wood-based panels and non-wood materials. Items with screws or nails were classified as non-wood. Each fraction was then weighed to quantify its share in the waste stream, providing measured data on real material flows handled by recycling operators.

Sampling focused on two key flows in the French recovered wood classification, Class B recovered and discarded furniture waste (DEA). Class B covers most wood waste, excluding packaging (Class A) and preservative treated wood (Class C). DEA is a subset of Class B and mainly includes discarded furniture. Across all samples fibreboard accounted for 4.5% by mass, while solid wood represented 55%, other wood-based panels (WBPs) 36.5% and non-wood materials 4%. Fibreboard content was higher in DEA than in Class B (8.4% versus 3.4%) showing differences between the two waste flows.

Detailed results of sorting fibreboard particles with or without attached finish, data: ESB

Fibreboard with coating

30 kg -----> 60%

Pure fibreboard

20 kg -----> 40%

MAIN RESULTS

On average, the sampled wood piles contained 4.5% fibreboard by mass. This is relevant for particleboard manufacturers, who typically aim to keep fibreboard in recycled wood inputs below 3%. In the analysed material, around 60% of the fibreboard particles carried surface finishes. This matters because uncoated fibreboard is generally easier to recycle than coated fibreboard. Further grinding to smaller particle size would likely increase the share of uncoated fibreboard particles. To complement these measurements, ESB and FCBA use the EcoReFibre model to estimate when fibreboard placed on the market becomes waste. For France, the model closely matched the measured fibreboard share, although it slightly overestimated it. This supports the robustness of the model and strengthening confidence in future availability of waste fibreboard for recycling.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based and carbon storing material, wood is a key driver for Europe's circular bioeconomy. Reintegrating post-consumer solid wood and WBPs into the manufacture of particleboard closes material loops and extends the lifespan of wood. Consequently, material value is maintained and the dependence on virgin wood is reduced. EcoRefibre has developed an innovative waste sorting line and smart recycling technologies to enable end-of-life fibreboards to be broken down into fibres which are then reintegrated into new products. From an economic perspective, increasing recycling can help broaden the raw material base and improve the availability of raw materials. Of course, investments in recycling equipment and process adaption are required for industrial-scale production. The ability of the above-described interactive tool to estimate future fibreboard waste availability for recycling will provide confidence to those wishing to investment in the developed recycling technologies and in market scale up.

By fostering a circular value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the EcoReFibre project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), while aligning with the upcoming Circular Economy Act (CEA).

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSSES THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

CONTACT

**ESB L'ECOLE SUPÉRIEURE
DU BOIS**

Nantes, France

Mark Irle
Research Director

mark.irle@esb-campus.fr

ESB on LinkedIn

esb-campus.fr

EcoReFibre on LinkedIn

**SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF
AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES**

Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos
Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se | slu.se

SLU on LinkedIn

slu.se

ecorefibre.eu

PARTNERS

ecorefibre.eu

Photo credits: Sonae Arauco, ESB, InnovaWood. Layout: Fovéa création.

This document reflects the authors' views only and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

**Funded by
the European Union**